

CoARA

Coalition for Advancing
Research Assessment

NATIONAL CHAPTERS

OVERVIEW

Andorra
Cyprus
Denmark
Finland
France
Germany
Hungary
Ireland
Italy
Netherlands
Norway
Poland
Portugal
Slovenia
Spain
Sweden
Switzerland
Ukraine
United Kingdom

Mission

The National Chapter aims to create a platform for Andorran members of CoARA to exchange knowledge and engage in mutual learning regarding issues unique to Andorra and other small countries and territories. This effort is aimed at integrating global principles into local contexts, covering aspects such as peer review processes, revisions to promotion criteria and alternative career pathways, ethical metrics, and a more coordinated and systematic approach toward reforming research assessment on a national level in line with European and international developments of the CoARA agreement.

Objectives

- Ensure mutual learning across institutions by sharing experiences and good practices
- Raise awareness about the reform of research assessment in other institutions of Andorra, as well as in international institutions
- Establish strategies to culturally adapt and incorporate global principles into local contexts
- Address multi- and interdisciplinary assessment
- Seek dialogue with researchers from different disciplines
- Encourage involvement of Andorran non-members of CoARA
- Host webinars and seminars
- Publish web pages and reports to communicate the diverse benefits of the reform, the progress at the national level, and international developments
- Collaborate with other NCs

Members

- Universitat d'Andorra (UdA) / University of Andorra (UdA)
- Agència de Qualitat de l'Ensenyament Superior d'Andorra
- (AQUA) / Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education in Andorra (AQUA)

Contact

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Mission

The University of Cyprus is the leading academic and research institution in Cyprus. It will participate in the National Chapter with two of its entities: The Research and Innovation Support Service, and the SInnoPSis research unit in Science and Innovation Policy and Studies formed in January 2022 as a result of the SInnoPSis ERA Chair funded project.

The participation of European Office of Cyprus (EOC) in the National CoARA Chapter of Cyprus is critical for maximising the impact for Cyprus R&I institutions in terms of knowledge transfer and the facilitation of the process.

Objectives

- UCY and EOC will lead the way and mentor other universities and research institutions to comprehend and endorse the CoARA vision and resulting transformations in research assessment

Members

- European Office of Cyprus
- University of Cyprus

 Contact

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Mission

The mission of the Danish National Chapter is to provide a national platform for CoARA in Denmark to engage key stakeholders, facilitate mutual exchange, share best practices, and to pave the way for developments in research assessment that both recognises the diversity of research activities, outputs, and practices, but also further drive quality in research.

Objectives

- Exchange of experiences and best practice procedures among institutions and funders
- Provide insight into research assessment procedures and practices among institutions
- Inspire and develop new ideas based on national as well as international initiatives
- Align research assessment procedures across institutions when relevant

Members

- Independent Research Fund Denmark
- Villum Foundation
- Aalborg University
- VELUX FONDEN
- Technical University of Denmark
- University of Southern Denmark
- Lundbeck Foundation
- Roskilde University
- Danish National Research Foundation

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Mission

The Chapter's mission is to support the entire Finnish research community in its journey towards a quality-focused assessment culture that recognises the full diversity and impact of academic work. The Finnish NC aims to raise awareness and discussions about the importance of approaches to assessment that incentivise, reflect and reward the plural characteristics of high quality research, in support of diverse, inclusive and open research cultures.

Objectives

- Engage all types of stakeholders in the movement for change
- Discover most responsible assessment approaches to, and to alleviate contradictions between, different assessment layers and processes, concerning individual researchers and research teams, research organisations and higher education institutions, of research infrastructures, research outputs and projects
- Facilitate effective and timely implementation of CoARA commitments

Members

- Aalto University
- Arcada University of Applied Sciences
- Åbo Akademi University
- Åland University of Applied Sciences
- Centria University of Applied Sciences
- Diaconia University of Applied Sciences
- Federation of Finnish Learned Societies
- Finnish Environment Institute
- Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare
- Finnish Union of Docents
- Geological Survey of Finland
- Haaga-Helia University of Applied Sciences
- Hanken School of Economics
- Helsinki University
- HUMAK University of Applied Sciences
- Häme University of Applied Sciences
- Jamk University of Applied Sciences
- Kajaani University of Applied Sciences
- Karelia University of Applied Sciences
- LAB University of Applied Sciences
- Lapland University of Applied Sciences
- Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology
- Laurea University of Applied Sciences
- Metropolia University of Applied Sciences
- Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke)
- NLS National Land Survey of Finland
- Novia University of Applied Sciences
- Oulu University of Applied Sciences
- Police University College
- Research Council of Finland
- Satakunta University of Applied Sciences

Members

- Savonia University of Applied Sciences
- Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences
- South-Eastern Finland University of Applied Sciences Xamk
- Tampere University
- Tampere University of Applied Sciences
- The University of the Arts Helsinki
- Turku University of Applied Sciences
- University of Eastern Finland
- University of Jyväskylä
- University of Lapland
- University of Oulu
- University of Turku
- University of Vaasa
- Vaasa University of Applied Sciences
- VTT Technical Research Centre
- Young Academy Finland

 Contact

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CoARA

National Chapter France

Mission

In France, various institutions conduct evaluations of different types: national research organisations, universities, evaluation and funding agencies, research units, research projects, recruitment and career promotion, bonuses, etc. The added value of the national chapter will be to create a common knowledge by sharing each process when establishing the French state of the art in each institution.

Objectives

- Coordinate French members' participation in CoARA, reporting and sharing information about CoARA's ongoing work, and particularly about the CoARA Working Groups
- Create synergies among specialists to avoid isolation within their functions
- Share information on the implementation of the CoARA commitments with French CoARA members
- Identify institutions' needs and help produce responses or resources to meet their needs
- Follow up the actions carried out among institutions and organisations in the national chapter

Members

- Aix-Marseille Université
- ANR
- ANRS
- CDEFI
- CNRS
- HCERES
- IFREMER
- INRIA
- INRAE
- INSERM
- Institut National du Cancer
- Sorbonne Université
- Université Claude Bernard, Lyon 1
- Université Clermont-Auvergne
- Université de Bordeaux
- Université de Haute Alsace
- Université de Lille
- Université de Lorraine
- Université de Paris-Saclay
- Université de Strasbourg
- Université Grenoble Alpes
- Université Paris-Nanterre
- Université Paris1 Panthéon Sorbonne
- Université Sorbonne Paris Nord

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Mission

The German National Chapter functions as a forum for the discussion and coordination of CoARA matters specific to the German research landscape. These topics could include assessment-relevant aspects of financial incentive structures inscribed in German (state or federal) law or statutes of universities and higher education institutions or associations, legislative developments or novel funding schemes of national importance.

Objectives

- The NC supports the reform of research assessment practices and culture in practical ways. The NC will function as a relevant actor in the research landscape, which can in itself strengthen the cultural change and allows the NC to advocate for specific goals
- The NC serves as a point of contact for German organisations that are interested in the topic of research assessment reform but are not – or not yet – signatories of ARRA or members of CoARA. On the one hand, this assists organisations that consider joining CoARA. On the other hand, German organisations which have voiced concerns over certain details of CoARA can be involved in the discussion.

Members

- Alexander von Humboldt Foundation
- Beilstein-Institut
- Berlin Institute of Health at Charité
- Berlin University Alliance
- Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin
- Darmstadt University of Applied Sciences
- Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (German Research Foundation, DFG) e.V.
- Deutsche Vereinigung für Sportwissenschaft e. V.
- European Molecular Biology Laboratory
- FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure
- Freie Universität Berlin
- German Association for Psychiatry, Psychotherapy and Psychosomatics
- German Psychological Society (DGPs)
- German Science and Humanities Council
- German Sport University Cologne
- German U15
- Helmholtz Open Science Office
- Hochschule Bonn-Rhein-Sieg University of Applied Sciences
- Hochschulallianz für den Mittelstand (HafM) e.V.
- Hochschullehrerbund Bundesvereinigung
- Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin
- Leibniz Association
- Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
- Leibniz University Hannover

Members

- Mainz University of Applied Sciences
- Max-Delbrück-Centrum für Molekulare Medizin in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft
- Ruhr University Bochum (RUB)
- RWTH Aachen University
- Technical University of Applied Sciences Amberg-Weiden
- Technische Universität Berlin
- Technische Universität Braunschweig
- TU Darmstadt
- TU Dortmund University
- University Alliance Ruhr
- Universität Freiburg
- Universität Hamburg
- University of Applied Science Jena
- University of Potsdam
- ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences

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Mission

The mission of the Hungarian National Chapter is to align the development and reform of assessment systems of Hungarian members, adhering to CoARA's commitments.

Objectives

- Initiate a discussion and exchange forum to establish the state of the art of research assessment in the participating institutions, evaluate the extent to which these are compliant or not with CoARA commitments
- Assess the feasible changes, and address the bottlenecks in their institutional implementation
- Identify external factors of influence on the change process
- Develop a database of tools and evaluation mechanisms aimed primarily to fill in institutional gaps, expand the inclusiveness of the national database used for assessment purposes
- Share good practices & optimise resources
- Evaluate new practices on an annual base and iteratively gather feedback from all stakeholders and compare with best practices at international level

Members

- Andrassy University Budapest
- Budapest University of Technology and Economics
- Corvinus University of Budapest
- Eötvös Loránd University
- HUN-REN HQ
- Hungarian Academy of Sciences
- Hungarian Accreditation Committee (MAB)
- Hungarian Rectors' Conference
- Jewish Theological Seminary – University of Jewish Studies, Hungary
- University of Debrecen
- Hungarian Young Academy
- University of Miskolc
- University of Pécs

 Contact

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Mission

The Chapter will provide a platform for Irish members of CoARA to exchange knowledge, mutual learning on issues that are specific to Ireland, such as peer review processes, revision of promotion criteria, Irish funding agency adoption of DORA and/or other statements on the responsible use of research metrics.

Objectives

- Building a network of diverse stakeholders from across the Irish research ecosystem
- Raising awareness and promote understanding of Responsible Research Assessment amongst the research community, taking on board the insights from this community on challenges faced across disciplines and career stages
- Supporting members to broaden what they value in research, while respecting that this may vary across organisations and disciplines.
- Sharing information on policies and practices to help develop national-level policies and best practice guidelines that align with the principles of RRA
- Advocating for appropriate funding to enable implementation of RRA
- Facilitating collaboration across Ireland and the CoARA network to further drive the RRA agenda

Members

- Dublin City University
- Health Research Board
- Irish Research Council
- Mary Immaculate College
- Science Foundation Ireland
- Southeast Technological University
- Technological University Dublin
- Technological University of the Shannon
- Trinity College Dublin
- University College Cork
- University College Dublin
- University of Galway
- University of Limerick

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Mission

In Italy there is an active ongoing debate about the methods used for research assessment, promoted by single institutions and associations. The NC functions as a coordinating body, moving forward the current state of the national debate and developing a practical implementation proposal. It will bring together different communities involved in research assessment and scholarly communication.

Objectives

- Enable mutual learning, share best practices, and raise awareness of best responsible assessment practices and indicators in the national community on the ongoing research assessment reform
- Foster discussion about reviewing and developing assessment criteria, tools and processes for assessing research institutions, individual researchers and projects
- Create an active network among Italian institutions, promoting the alignment of the Institutional Roadmaps requested by CoARA, and engaging with the relevant political decision-making national body(ies)
- Establish stable and bidirectional connections with the Working Groups, to explore the impact of their results on national practices and provide a feedback based on the experiences of the Italian communities on more specific topics
- Interact and collaborate with the other National Chapters

Members

- Agenzia nazionale di valutazione del sistema universitario e della ricerca – ANVUR
- Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna
- Associazione italiana per la promozione della scienza aperta – AISA
- Ca' Foscari Università di Venezia
- Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – CNR
- GRIN Gruppo di informatica
- IRCCS Ospedale San Raffaele
- Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia – IIT
- Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare – INFN
- Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia – INGV
- Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale – OGS
- Italian Reproducibility Network – ITRN
- IULM
- Politecnico di Bari
- Politecnico di Torino
- Scuola IMT Lucca
- Scuola Normale Superiore
- Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna
- Tuscan Organisation of Universities and Research for Europe – TOUR4EU
- Università "G. d'Annunzio" di Chieti-Pescara
- Università Campus Biomedico di Roma
- Università del Piemonte Orientale
- Università dell'Aquila
- Università dell'Insubria
- Università della Campania Luigi Vanvitelli
- Università della Tuscia
- Università di Bergamo
- Università di Brescia
- Università di Cagliari
- Università di Camerino

CoARA

National Chapter Italy

Members

- Università di Cassino e del Lazio meridionale
- Università di Ferrara
- Università di Firenze
- Università di Foggia
- Università di Macerata
- Università di Messina
- Università di Milano
- Università di Milano-Bicocca
- Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia
- Università di Padova
- Università di Palermo
- Università di Pavia
- Università di Pisa
- Università di Torino
- Università di Trento
- Università di Trieste
- Università di Urbino Carlo Bo
- Università di Verona
- Università per Stranieri di Siena
- Università Politecnica delle Marche
- Università Roma Tre
- Università Suor Orsola Benincasa

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Mission

In the Netherlands, public academic knowledge institutions voiced a common ambition to modernise the current recognition and rewards system. The NC offers a natural extension of these existing efforts and will function in the national programme as a knowledge hub for advancing research assessment, both in the Netherlands and abroad.

Objectives

- Create an active and open forum for knowledge exchange among Dutch CoARA members, as well as interested organisations outside the network.
- Link the CoARA commitments to relevant developments in the Netherlands, such as, assessments of research units following the Strategy, Evaluation Protocol and the national UAS Sector Protocol for Quality Assurance in research, creating diversity in career paths and recognising and rewarding Open Science.

Members

- Universities of the Netherlands (UNL)
- Netherlands Federation of University Medical Centres (NFU)
- Utrecht University
- Maastricht University
- University of Amsterdam
- Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
- Twente University
- Leiden University
- TU Delft
- Radboud University
- TU Eindhoven
- Wageningen University and Research
- Open Universiteit
- Tilburg University
- Erasmus University Rotterdam
- University of Humanistic Studies
- University of Groningen
- Erasmus MC
- UMC Utrecht
- UMC Groningen
- The Dutch Research Council (NWO)
- ZonMw
- The Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW)
- Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences
- Saxion University of Applied Science

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Mission

The NORCAM National Chapter is a network organised by Universities Norway. Most Norwegian institutions are already working to implement the principles of NORCAM, which is highly aligned with the principles of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) and CoARA. By working with NORCAM, the members are also meeting the expectations in both core and supporting commitments of ARRA.

Objectives

- To share experiences and best practices on the development of institutional versions of the NORCAM framework
- To create an arena for discussing and sharing practical and strategic aspects of the European Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) and the work and processes linked to CoARA, both for the institutions and organisations that have signed the agreement and for those who are considering this

Members

- Inland Norway University of Applied Sciences
- Lovisenberg Diaconal Hospital
- MF Norwegian School of Theology, Religion and Society
- Molde University College
- NIFU Nordic Institute for Studies of Innovation, Research and Education
- Norwegian Research Council
- Norwegian University of Life Sciences NMBU
- NTNU
- Oslo Metropolitan University
- The Norwegian School of Sport Sciences
- The Young Academy of Norway (AYF)
- UiT The Arctic University of Norway
- Universities Norway
- University of Agder
- University of Bergen
- University of Oslo
- University of South-Eastern Norway
- University of Stavanger
- VID Specialized University
- Østfold University College

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Mission

The Polish National Chapter was initiated by the Jagiellonian University and the Koszalin University of Technology, under the auspices of the Conference of Rectors of Academic Schools in Poland and the Polish Academy of Sciences, to monitor the commitments declared by individual signatories so that they are coherent and complementary. The focus will be set on the scope and feasibility of peer-review in the evaluation of researchers and research performing institutions, as well as on how the reform can be used to initiate changes in the legal framework and research culture towards promoting cutting-edge studies conducted in the long-term perspective.

Objectives

- Assess the coherence of the solutions agreed within the Coalition with the current national regulations
- Balance common principles and institutional autonomy

Members

- Academy of Physical Education in Katowice
- AGH University of Science and Technology
- Andrzej Frycz Modrzewski Krakow University
- Bialystok University of Technology
- Conference of Rectors of Academic Schools in Poland
- Foundation for Polish Science
- FRP Polish Rectors Foundation
- Gdansk University of Technology
- Institute of Philosophy and Sociology PAS
- Institute of Polish Language PAS
- Institute of Rural and Agricultural Development PAS
- Jagiellonian University
- Jan Dlugosz University in Czestochowa
- Jozef Pilsudski University of Physical Education in Warsaw
- Kazimierz Wielki University
- Koszalin University of Technology
- Lodz University of Technology
- Maria Curie-Sklodowska University
- Maria Grzegorzewska University
- Medical University of Gdansk
- Medical University of Warsaw
- National Information Processing Institute
- National Representation of Doctoral Students
- Polish Young Academy (of PAS)
- Polish-Japanese Academy of Information Technology
- Politechnika Krakowska im. Tadeusza Kosciuszki
- Poznan University of Economics and Business
- Rzeszow University of Technology
- SGH Warsaw School of Economics
- Silesian University of Technology
- SWPS University of Social Sciences and Humanities

Members

- SWPS University of Social Sciences and Humanities (now: Jan Dlugosz University in Czestochowa)
- The Institute of Literary Research PAS
- The John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin
- The Open Science Competence Network – Data Steward PL
- The Polish Academy of Sciences
- The Strzeminski Academy of Fine Arts Lodz
- UKSW Cardinal Stefan Wyszynski University in Warsaw
- University of Agriculture in Krakow
- University of Bialystok
- University of Gdansk
- University of Lodz
- University of Opole
- University of Rzeszow
- University of Silesia in Katowice
- University of Warsaw
- Vistula University
- West Pomeranian University of Technology
- Wroclaw Medical University
- Wroclaw University of Economics and Business
- Wroclaw University of Environmental and Life Sciences
- Wroclaw University of Health and Sport Sciences
- WSB University

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Mission

The Portuguese National Chapter is a collaborative platform that will enhance and contextualise CoARA's commitments of the debate on research assessment reform within the Portuguese research landscape, while bringing the Agreement to the forefront of ongoing national initiatives.

Objectives

- Raise awareness within the national community to the Agreement principles and CoARA's commitments to action (Commitment 7)
- Enable mutual learning and the communication of progress in implementing member institutions' Roadmaps and action plans, as well as their collaboration in CoARA's Working Groups (WGs), thereby contributing to the advancement of reform on an integrated and national scale (Commitments 3, 8 & 9)
- Promote and engage with research on research (RoR) activities, particularly on peer review processes and the development of alternative/new assessment criteria, tools, or processes, discussing and disseminating best practices across the areas of publishing, career recruitment and promotion, and funding (Commitments 1, 2 & 6)
- Collaborate and share insights with other NCs and relevant CoARA WGs (Commitment 3)
- Analyse how CoARA's commitments align with national legislation and identify any barriers or constraints, establishing synergies with the objectives of ERA Action 3

Members

- CES Centro de Estudos Sociais
- CIAC Centro de Investigação em Artes e Comunicação
- FCT Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia
- I3S Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde
- ICAREHB Centro Interdisciplinar de Arqueologia e Evolução do Comportamento Humano
- INESC Brussels HUB
- INESC-ID Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Investigação e Desenvolvimento em Lisboa
- INESC MN Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores para os Microsistemas e Nanotecnologias
- INESC TEC Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Tecnologia e Ciência
- Instituto Politécnico de Setúbal
- ISCTE – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa
- Universidade Aberta
- Universidade do Algarve
- Universidade de Aveiro
- Universidade Católica Portuguesa
- Universidade de Coimbra
- Universidade de Évora
- Universidade de Lisboa
- Universidade Lusíada
- Universidade Lusófona
- Universidade do Minho
- Universidade Nova de Lisboa
- Universidade do Porto
- Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro

 Contact

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Mission

The Slovenian National Chapter aims to support Slovenia's national research assessment reform by fostering dialogue among various academic stakeholders. The NC's mission is to provide a collaborative platform for discussions and knowledge sharing that would help implement a comprehensive, quality-focused research assessment framework that respects research autonomy, diversity, and the impact of research outputs.

Objectives

- Establish a broader, comprehensive, and quality-focused assessment framework, while recognising the autonomy of research organisations, freedom of scientific research, and diversity of research activities and impacts.
- Help research organisations, authorities, and other academic stakeholders to adopt the CoARA Agreement, principles, and commitments and to put them into practice.
- Raise awareness of international best practices in responsible assessment and set the stage to integrate them into the Slovenian research environment.

Members

- Slovenina Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)
- Educational Research Institute
- Institute of Contemporary History
- Jožef Stefan Institute
- The Young Academy of Slovenia
- University of Ljubljana
- University of Maribor
- University of Novo Mesto

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Mission

The National Chapter Spain is jointly led by the Conference of Rectors of Spanish Universities (CRUE), the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), the Carlos III Health Institute (ISCIII), and the National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation of Spain (ANECA). Its mission is to support the reform of research assessment in Spain, recognising the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research.

Objectives

- Create a joint initiative to promote and support the revision and development of the research assessment criteria, tools, and processes in Spain, in line with the Agreement principles and criteria described in the four core commitments
- Engage with research performing and research funding organisations, evaluation agencies, and researchers' associations in Spain
- Enable mutual learning within the Chapter and in collaboration with the CoARA working groups

Members

Co-chairs of the National Chapter:

- The Conference of Rectors of Spanish Universities (CRUE)
- Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)
- Carlos III Health Institute (ISCIII)
- National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation of Spain (ANECA)

National Chapter Members:

- Agencia para la Calidad Científica y Universitaria de Andalucía (ACCUA)
- ACPUA – Agencia de Calidad y Prospectiva Universitaria de Aragón
- Agencia Canaria de Calidad Universitaria y Evaluación Educativa (ACCUEE)
- Agencia de Calidad Universitaria de las Illes Balears
- Axencia para a Calidade do Sistema Universitario de Galicia (ACSUG)
- Agencia para la Calidad del Sistema Universitario de Castilla y León (ACSUCyL)
- Agència per a la Qualitat del Sistema Universitari de Catalunya (AQU Catalunya)
- Agència de Qualitat i Avaluació Sanitàries de Catalunya (AQuAS)
- Asociación de Mujeres Investigadoras y Tecnólogas (AMIT)
- AVAP – Agencia Valenciana d'Avaluació i Prospectiva
- BarcelonaBeta Brain Research Center (BBRC)
- Centre de Recerca Matemàtica (CRM)
- Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG)
- Centro de Investigación Ecológica y Aplicaciones Forestales (CREAF)
- Confederación de Sociedades Científicas de España (COSCE)
- EU-LIFE
- Fundació Foment de la Investigació Sanitària i Biomèdica Comunitat Valenciana
- Fundació Pasqual Maragall
- Fundación Agencia Aragonesa para la Investigación y el Desarrollo (ARAID)
- Fundación Española para la Ciencia y Tecnología (FECYT)
- Fundación para el Conocimiento madri+d
- Fundación para la Investigación Biomédica del Hospital Universitario La Paz
- Fundación Universidad Católica de Valencia San Vicente Mártir
- Fundación Universidad San Jorge
- Institució CERCA
- Institut Català de Nanociència i Nanotecnologia (ICN2)

CoARA

National Chapter Spain

Members

- Institut d'Investigacions Biomèdiques August Pi i Sunyer (IDIBAPS)
- Institut de Bioenginyeria de Catalunya
- Institut de Recerca en Energia de Catalunya (IREC)
- Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria Biodonostia (IIS Biodonostia)
- IR Sant Pau – Institut de Recerca Sant Pau
- ISGlobal – Barcelona Institute for Global Health
- Red de Bibliotecas Universitarias Españolas (REBIUN)
- Sociedad Científica Informática de España (SCIE)
- Unibasq – Agencia de Calidad del Sistema Universitario Vasco
- Universidad Alfonso X El Sabio
- Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona
- Universidad Autónoma de Madrid
- Universidad Camilo José Cela
- Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
- Universidad Católica San Antonio de Murcia
- Universidad Católica Santa Teresa de Jesús de Ávila
- Universidad CEU Cardenal Herrera
- Universidad Complutense de Madrid
- Universidad de Alcalá
- Universidad de Alicante
- Universidad de Almería
- Universidad de Burgos
- Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha
- Universidad de Córdoba
- Universidad de Deusto
- Universidad de Extremadura
- Universidad de Jaén
- Universidad de La Laguna
- Universidad de La Rioja
- Universidad de Málaga
- Universidad de Murcia
- Universidad de Navarra
- Universidad de Oviedo
- Universidad de Salamanca
- Universidad de Sevilla
- Universidad de Zaragoza
- Universidad del País Vasco / Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea
- Universidad Internacional de La Rioja
- Universidad Internacional de Valencia
- Universidad Loyola de Andalucía
- Universidad Miguel Hernández de Elche
- Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED)
- Universidad Nebrija
- Universidad Pablo de Olavide
- Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena
- Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
- Universidad Pontificia Comillas
- Universidad Rey Juan Carlos
- Universidad San Pablo CEU
- Universidade de A Coruña
- Universidade de Santiago de Compostela
- Universidade de Vigo
- Universitat Abat Oliba CEU
- Universitat de Barcelona
- Universitat de Girona
- Universitat de les Illes Balears
- Universitat de Lleida
- Universitat de València
- Universitat de Vic – Central University of Catalonia
- Universitat Jaume I
- Universitat Oberta de Catalunya
- Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya
- Universitat Politècnica de València
- Universitat Ramon Llull
- Universitat Rovira i Virgili
- Vall d'Hebron Institut de Recerca

Contact

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Mission

The National Chapter Sweden, comprising SUHF (the Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions) and national research funders, aims to find common grounds on the definitions and criteria how to assess research in the future. In 2022, SUHF appointed a working group with the task of developing a national framework for merit assessment at Swedish higher education institutions, triggered also by the call for an updated Open Science strategy. Since this work is not only focusing on research merits but university teachers and researchers' full-ranged achievements, major funders are not actively participating in this work.

Objectives

- To foster parallel work focusing on research merits and promoting the exchange of experiences and models for successful management and implementation of new standards between universities and funders
- Identify common standards for assessment of research within the Swedish research landscape
- Bring together the overall national efforts and outputs through the National chapter
- Actively contribute on-going work, best practices, and case studies to the broader CoARA community

Members

- Dalarna University
- Karolinska Institutet (KI)
- Karlstad University
- Kristianstad University
- Knowledge Foundation (KK-stiftelsen)
- Linköping University
- Linnaeus University
- Lund University
- Malmö University
- Mid Sweden University
- Open Science Community Sweden
- Research Sweden
- Royal Institute of Technology (KTH)
- SciLifeLab
- Swedish Governmental Agency for Innovative Systems (Vinnova)
- Swedish Higher Education Authority (UKÄ) (observer)
- Swedish Reproducibility Network
- Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare (Forte)
- Swedish Research Council for the Environment, Agricultural Science and Spatial Planning (Formas)
- Swedish Research Council, SRC (Vetenskapsrådet)
- Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU)
- Södertörn University
- Stockholm University
- The Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions, SUHF
- The Young Academy of Sweden
- Umeå University
- University of Gävle

 Contact

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Mission

The National Chapter brings together Swiss cantonal and federal universities, universities of applied sciences and funders, covering Switzerland's different language regions and reflecting the variety of its Higher Education and Research landscape. While the different institutions have been engaged in individual initiatives fostering Open Science, EDI and/or responsible research assessment more generally and plan to be involved in different CoARA working groups, the Swiss National Chapter will ensure a more coordinated and systematic approach towards reforming research assessment on a national level, in line with European and international developments.

Objectives

- Ensure mutual learning across institutions by sharing experiences and good practices
- Align approaches whenever possible while respecting the autonomy of all institutions involved
- Raise awareness about the reform of research assessment in relevant communities in Switzerland
- Seek dialogue with researchers from different disciplines
- Encourage involvement of non-members of CoARA

Members

- Bern University of Applied Sciences (BFH)
- University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland (HES-SO)
- University of Fribourg
- ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences
- Swiss National Science Foundation
- Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences
- Swiss Reproducibility Network

 Contact

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Mission

The mission of the Ukrainian National Chapter is to advance the growth of Ukraine's knowledge-driven economy for post-war recovery by reforming the country's research and higher education system through advancing research assessment based on CoARA principles and prioritising Open Science.

Objectives

- Adapt the CoARA best practices to Ukrainian reality, especially for various research fields and career stages
- Coordinate national efforts in CoARA principles implementation and related discussion while providing expert support to Ukrainian authorities
- Discuss and experiment with (open) peer review as the central instrument for qualitative evaluation of research

Members

- All-Ukrainian NGO "Innovative University"
- Institute for Open Science and Innovation
- Institute of Higher Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine
- Lutsk National Technical University
- National Research Foundation of Ukraine
- NGO Growth Pole

 Contact

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Mission

The UK National Chapter aims to expand as the number of UK CoARA members/signatories increases. In time and with proper resourcing, the remit of the Chapter could widen to address particular needs in the UK R&D sector. The Chapter seeks to support the development of a renewed UK Forum for Responsible Research Assessment (replacing the previous UK Forum for Responsible Research Metrics as recommended in 'Harnessing the Metric Tide'). There are clear synergies between this and a CoARA National Chapter in terms of providing a forum for consultation, deliberation, advocacy and evidence-informed advice related to responsible research assessment.

Objectives

- Facilitating meaningful change by supporting member and signatory organisations to reflect on ambitions for reform of research assessment and put principles into practice, e.g. through the development and implementation of action plans
- Promoting systemic reform by engaging with those outside of the Coalition and supporting potential UK CoARA members and signatories to understand the implications of signing and/or joining CoARA

Members

- Brunel University London
- CRAC-Vitae
- City, University of London
- Goldsmiths College, University of London
- Health Data Research UK
- Health Sciences University
- Jisc
- John Innes Centre
- Loughborough University
- Manchester Metropolitan University
- Nottingham Trent University
- Queen Mary University of London
- Research on Research Institute (RoRI)
- Society of Spanish Researchers in the United Kingdom (SRUK/CERU)
- Software Sustainability Institute
- Swansea University
- The Association of Research Managers and Administrators (ARMA UK)
- UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN)
- University of Bristol
- University of Central Lancashire
- University of Derby
- University of Edinburgh
- University of Hertfordshire
- University of Manchester
- University of Reading
- University of Suffolk
- University of Strathclyde
- University of Warwick

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CoARA

Coalition for Advancing
Research Assessment

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